

Managing Editor's Column

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Dear Readers:

This issue is a very special one. It contains extended versions of all five ICCE Outstanding Award Winning papers which were presented at the ICCE/ICCAI 2000 conference in Taipei, Taiwan. I want to thank ICCE for allowing us to offer this special treat to J.UCS readers, and the authors for their willingness to rework their papers for J.UCS.

Note that ICCE, the International Conference for Computers in Education, takes place in Korea this year, see <http://www.icce2001.org>. This will again be a remarkable conference!

I am happy to report that we are also in the process of preparing three special issues for May, June and July. More on this next month!

Enjoy J.UCS, and don't forget to renew your subscriptions!

Cordially,

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